

Effects of Audio-Visual Aids on Academic Achievement in Computer Studies among Secondary School Students in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

The evolution of audio-visual aids has made it very possible for learners to become more involved in learning activity. This study investigates the effects of audio-visual Aids (AVA) on academic achievement in computer studies among secondary schools' students in North- west Nigeria. The research design adopted was quasi-experimental research design, specifically pretest posttest non randomized control group design, three research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class two (SSII) computer students in North-West Nigeria during the 2022/2023 academic session. 700 (350 male and 350 female) students constitute the sample size of the study, this was arrived at using multi-stage sampling technique within all the seven states in North-west Nigeria. Computer achievement test (COMSAT) was used to collect data for the study. The COMSAT was validated and reliability coefficient of 0.05 was obtained using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) reliability test. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions. The analysis indicated that AVA had significant effects on students' cognitive achievement in computer studies. Gender was a significant factor in the students' overall cognitive achievement in computer studies. Thus, it is recommended to use AVA in the teaching and learning of computer and audio-visual aids should be procured and distributed in all the secondary schools in North Western Nigeria.

Keywords: Audio-visual, teaching, learning, computer, school.

Introduction

The innovation in technology has revolutionized the 21st-century educational workforce, changing the way things are done and equip teaching staff with the requisite skills needed to become more productive and effective educators (Toliver, 2017). Malmi, Sheard, Kinnunen, Simon and Sinclair (2019) stated that computer studies is a programme of study designed to give the students a thoroughly but general grounding in the ways computers are used. Computer studies equips the students with knowledge, skills and competencies that will enable them to operate the computer efficiently. Over the years, students' response to computer studies especially in public schools has been poor and the reason seems to be that instructional materials specifically audio-visual materials may not have been used or properly utilized during instruction and this is a source of worry to the researchers considering its possible effects on students' achievement in the subject. The evolution of audio-visual materials aids has made it very possible for learners to become more involved in learning activity (Idris, Shamsuddin, Arome & Aminu, 2018). Meaningful learning is most likely to occur when information is presented in a potentially meaningful way that the information conveyed is made or presented in a way that the majority of what was taught remains permanent in the learners' memory. Similarly, Soumia, (2020) opined that Audio-Visual aids make students understand and retains what they were taught for long.

Bhardwaj (2020) defines Audio-Visual Aids as "training or educational materials directed at both the senses of hearing and the sense of sight, films, recordings, photographs, etc. used in classroom instructions, library collections or the likes".

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Audio-visual materials could also be defined as the supplementary materials which are used to facilitate learning; which include models, diagrams, and displays as well as, recently developed taped-recording devices, film and television. It is a combination of aural and vision or a merger of spoken words and related visual aids to affect permanent and relative change in behaviour as reflected in sound-image display in television, film-show, video and sponsored-talking books (Karami, 2019). According to Padhi (2021), audio-visual materials are instructional devices which are used to communicate messages more effectively through sound and visuals. Audio-visual materials help in stimulating the sensory organs like ears and eyes and facilitate quick comprehension of the message by the audience. These may be used for literate as well as illiterate people. Audio-visual materials are used to improve teaching, i.e. to increase the correctness, clarity, and effectiveness of the ideas and skills being transferred. They enable the learner to LOOK, LISTEN, AND LEARN; to learn faster, to learn more, to learn thoroughly and to remember longer. Ojetade and Aregbesola (2020) supported the above with their findings that reviewed that audio-visual material has significant effect on student's achievement in science. Ibe and Abamu (2019) also revealed that students that were exposed to lesson with audio-visual technological contents integrated achieve higher in test scores than the group not exposed to audio visual materials. Singh (2021) found similar results in their study. They found that audio-visual materials can make lessons easy to understand. Images that a student views on the screen can be easily comprehended and remembered than descriptive reading materials. The importance of audio-visual materials in the teaching and learning processes cannot be over emphasized.

According to Poonia (2020), the roles of audio-visual materials are provision of sensory experience which requires an adequate background of sensory experience, which implies new words and unfamiliar objects cannot be followed and understood properly unless they are attached to specific elements of one's experience; provision of substitutes for direct experiences which makes audio-visual materials to come to our aid at that time to facilitate understanding of new concepts, facts and symbols. Pictures, models and specimens and so on to be used as accurate and effective substitutes of direct learning experiences; supplement to direct experience by visiting a post office or a cotton textile mill, pupils can learn more about the postal system and about the manufacture of cloth if these direct learning experiences are followed by seeing a film or motion picture on the subject; Important motivators by possess vividness, clarity and dramatic appeal. Children enjoy looking at pictures, going to movies and listening to radio. These are the effective medium of holding the attention and to simulating new interests and activities among children; Effective aid to the slow learner by making them to understand more easily and remember the facts, gained through pictures, movies, models and radio etc. than gathered from abstract symbols and printed pages; More efficient learning by making them to remember the facts, thus learned, for longer period; Development of the power of imagination and observation that are much clearer and more effective than the verbal images, which makes learning more natural and easier. Hence, the study is to investigate the effects of the use of audio-visual materials on students' achievement in computer studies.

The absence of the use of audio-visual materials by the secondary school teachers is a contributory factor to level of achievement of secondary school students in computer studies, which may be attributed to lack of interest on the part of the learners. Soumia, (2020) opined that Audio-Visual aids make students understand and retains what they were taught for long. Despite the fact that educational aids have a lot of outstanding positive effect in teaching and learning, the use of conventional approach to instruction are still what teachers are using, which is not based in sense experience nor does it extend their experience. In view of all this, learning of such cannot be permanent. Yet, there is also evidence of non-availability and underutilization of audio-visual materials in schools, these has led to students lack of interest, attention and active participation in the teaching and learning exercise which might be responsible for the poor academic performance of students generally. These have greatly affected students' achievement in computer education. The problem now is will the use of audio-visual materials effectively improve students' achievement in computer studies?

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to find out the effects of audio-visual aids on academic achievement in computer studies among secondary students. The work specifically;

1. Determine the achievement scores of students taught computer studies using audio-visual aid and those exposed to lecture teaching method
2. Determine the mean achievement score of male and female students taught Computer Studies using audio-visual materials
3. Determine the interactive effect of method and gender on academic achievement in computer studies among secondary students

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Research Questions

Three research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the mean achievement scores of students taught computer studies using audio-visual aid and those exposed to lecture teaching method?
2. What is the mean achievement score of male and female students taught Computer Studies using Audio-Visual Aids?
3. What is the interactive effect of method and Gender on academic achievement in computer studies among secondary students?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of students taught Computer Studies using audio-visual aids and those taught using conventional teaching method.
2. There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Computer Studies using audio-visual aids.
3. There is no significant relationship between gender and method on students' mean achievement scores in Computer Studies.

Methodology

The research design adopted was quasi-experimental research design, specifically pretest posttest non randomized control group design. The researchers sampled fourteen secondary schools in North West Nigeria. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class two (SSII) computer students in North-West Nigeria during the 2022/2023 academic session. 700 (350 male and 350 female) students constitute the sample size of the study. This was arrived at using multi-stage sampling technique within all the seven states in North-west Nigeria. The instruments for this research were Audio-Visual Package for Computer Studies Instruction (AVPCSI) for the treatment group and Computer Studies Conventional Instruction Package (COMSCIP) for the control group. The test instrument, Computer Studies Achievement Test (COMSAT) were subjected to both face and content validation. The treatment instrument, Audio-Visual Package for Computer Studies Instruction (AVPCSI) was properly scrutinized by an expert in Educational Technology. The research questions were analysed using mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha levels using the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) on the post-test and pre-test scores as covariates. ANCOVA was deemed appropriate here because it served as procedure for controlling the initial difference across the groups as well as increasing the precision due to the existence of erroneous variables, thereby reducing error variance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean achievement score of students taught computer studies using audio-visual aid and those exposed to lecture teaching method?

Table 1: Mean scores of students based on treatment

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Experimental Group	371	70	196	19.28	4.716
Control Group	329	42	157	14.00	3.630
Valid N (listwise)	329				

Table 1 shows that the use of audio-visual aids had a huge effect on the academic achievement of the students. The students in the experimental group who were taught using audio-visual aids had a higher mean achievement score (19.28) than their counterparts in the control group who were taught using the conventional teaching method (14.00).

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Research Question 2

What is the mean achievement score of male and female students taught Computer Studies using Audio-Visual Aids?

Table 2: Mean achievement score of male and female students taught using audio-visual materials (AVPCSI).

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Male	210	84	196	21.23	4.415
Female	161	70	168	16.74	3.864
Valid N (listwise)	161				

As evident in Table 2, the male students exposed to **AVPCSI** obtained a mean score of 21.23 with a standard deviation of 4.415, while the female students also exposed to AVPCSI obtained a mean score of 16.74 with a standard deviation of 3.864. The study reported that the male students exposed to Audio-visual Package for Computer Studies Instruction achieved better than their female counterparts exposed to the same treatment.

Research Question 3

What is the interactive effect of method and Gender on academic achievement in computer studies among secondary students?

Table 3: The interactive effect of method and gender on students' achievement in computer studies.

Group	Male	Female	Mean Difference (Method)
Experimental (AVPCSI)	21.23	16.74	4.49
Control (CTM)	14.04	13.95	0.09
Mean Difference (Gender)	7.19	2.78	

Table 3 shows that, the male students exposed to **AVPCSI** obtained a mean score of 21.23, while the female students also exposed to AVPCSI obtained a mean score of 16.74, they have a mean difference of 4.29. From the control group, those exposed to the Conventional Teaching Method (CTM), the male students obtained a mean of 14.04 and the female students obtained a mean of 13.95, with a mean difference of 0.09. Comparing the two results from method (AVPCSI and CTM), it is observed that those exposed to Audio-Visual Package for Computer Studies Instruction achieved better than those exposed to the conventional teaching method. The males from the experimental group also showed a remarkable measure of understanding more than the females. Their mean differences in gender are also evident. The male students from the experimental group obtained a mean score of 21.23 while their male counterparts in the control group obtained a mean score of 14.04 with their mean difference summing up to 7.19. This shows that the males exposed to AVPCSI achieved better than the males exposed to CTM. Comparing the mean difference of the females as well from the experimental group and the control group, the females from the experimental had a mean of 16.74 while the females from the control group had a mean of 13.95 with their mean difference summing up to 2.78. The females increase in achievement was evident but not as much as that of the males.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of students taught Computer Studies using audio-visual aids and those taught using conventional teaching method.

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Table 4: ANCOVA results based on method (treatment vs control)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1337.720 ^a	2	668.860	57.914	.000
Intercept	81.165	1	81.165	7.028	.009
Pretest	642.475	1	642.475	55.629	.000
Group	84.337	1	84.337	7.302	.008
Error	1120.280	97	11.549		
Total	30682.000	100			
Corrected Total	2458.000	99			

a. R Squared = .544 (Adjusted R Squared = .535)

In Table 4, the calculated F value is 7.302 with a significance of 0.008. The significance of F is less than the alpha level (0.05), which means that it is significant. Therefore, we reject hypothesis one and accept the alternative hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught using audio-visual material and those taught using conventional teaching method.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Computer Studies using audio-visual aids.

Table 5: ANCOVA results showing the effects of gender on the mean achievement scores of the students taught computer using audio-visual materials.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	490.098 ^a	2	245.049	18.379	.000
Intercept	87.729	1	87.729	6.580	.013
Pretest	227.144	1	227.144	17.036	.000
Gender	171.759	1	171.759	12.882	.001
Error	666.657	50	13.333		
Total	20864.000	53			
Corrected Total	1156.755	52			

a. R Squared = .424 (Adjusted R Squared = .401)

As shown in Table 5, the calculated F value as 12.882 with a significance of 0.001. The significance of F is less than the alpha level (0.05), which means that it is significant. Therefore, we reject hypothesis two and accept the alternative hypothesis. Hence, there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught using audio-visual material as shown in table 2. The male students exposed to the use of audio-visual aids achieved higher than their female counterparts.

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Hypothesis 3

There is no significant relationship between gender and method on students’ mean achievement scores in Computer Studies.

Table 6: ANCOVA results showing the interaction of gender and method on the mean achievement of students in computer studies.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1505.461 ^a	4	376.365	37.536	.000
Intercept	108.156	1	108.156	10.787	.001
Pretest	547.177	1	547.177	54.572	.000
Group	81.864	1	81.864	8.165	.005
Gender	75.173	1	75.173	7.497	.007
Group * Gender	85.089	1	85.089	8.486	.004
Error	952.539	95	10.027		
Total	30682.000	100			
Corrected Total	2458.000	99			

a. R Squared = .612 (Adjusted R Squared = .596)

As shown in Table 6 the calculated F value is 8.486 with a significance of 0.004. The significance of F is less than the alpha level (0.05), which means that it is significant. Therefore, we reject hypothesis three and accept the alternative hypothesis. Hence, there is a significant interaction between gender and method on students’ mean achievement in computer education.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the effects of audio-visual aids on academic achievement in computer studies among secondary school students in North -West Nigeria. The results revealed that the use of audio-visual material had a huge effect on the academic achievement of the students. The result of the analysis of covariance on the performance of students taught computer using audio visual materials and those taught with conventional classroom instruction indicated a significant difference in favour of the students in the experimental groups. The students in this group achieved very much better than those taught conventionally. This is in line with the findings of Nonso, Onyebuanyi and Promise (2022) whose study concluded that audio-visual materials are very important and useful in education because learners gain more understanding in terms of multiple impression recorded through the eye, ear, touch and other series.

The influence of gender on the academic achievement of students when taught with audio-visual instructional material was examined using hypotheses two and three. The result of the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) showed significant gender difference for learners exposed to audio-visual instructional material. These findings showed that gender had influence on the performance of students in computer. Thus, it can be deduced that the use of audio-visual instructional material enhanced the achievement of both male and female students but the males achieved better.

The finding in Table 3 showed significant interaction between gender and method on students mean achievement in computer studies. the male students exposed to AVPCSI obtained a mean score of 21.23, while the female students also exposed to AVPCSI obtained a mean score of 16.74. They have a mean difference of 4.29. From the control group (those exposed to the conventional teaching method), the male students obtained a mean of 14.04 and the female students obtained a mean of 13.95, with a mean difference of 0.09. Comparing the results from the two methods (AVPCSI and CTM), it is observed that those exposed to Audio-visual Package for Computer Studies Instruction achieved better than those exposed to the Conventional Teaching Method. The males from the experimental group also showed a remarkable measure of understanding more than the females. Their mean differences in gender are also evident. The male students from the experimental group obtained a mean score of 21.23 while their male counterparts in the control group obtained a mean score of 14.04 with their mean difference summing up to 7.19. This shows that the males exposed to AVPCSI achieved better than the males exposed to CTM. Comparing the mean difference of the females as well from the experimental group and control, the females from the experimental had a mean of 16.74 while the females from the control group had a mean of 13.95 with their mean difference summing up to 2.78. The females increase in achievement was evident but not as much as that of the males.

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Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrated that audio-visual aids (AVA) were effective instructional technique for teaching computer studies. The results were in consonance with the result of research on the effectiveness of AVA for better student's achievement in science and mathematics carried out by Sutthikun, Poramatworachote, Unchai and Ketsiri (2023). It can therefore be concluded that a relationship exists between the use of audio-visual aids and achievement of students in computer studies. Results of the study also showed that there was a significant difference between male and female students' achievement in computer studies when exposed to the treatment. Furthermore, AVA can be used as an alternative instructional method to the conventional method of teaching the various topics in computer studies since it proved to be more effective. The study has therefore provided strong evidence of the usefulness of AVA in teaching and learning of computer studies.

Recommendations

From the results of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Audio-visual aids are not always readily available for the teachers to use despite the fact that most of them know how to manipulate them. They should be procured and distributed in all the secondary schools in North Western Nigeria.
2. Teachers should be encouraged to devise local improvised audio-visual aids for teaching computer studies.
3. Computer students should be introduced to audio-visual aid as a tool for meaningful learning.
4. Computer education researchers may replicate and improve upon this study by conducting it among larger sample size and at other educational levels in the nations' educational system.

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